

Refractory phosphorus in the HD 100546 protoplanetary disc

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ABSTRACT

The phosphorus budget of planets is intertwined with their formation history and is thought to influence their habitability. The chemical reservoirs and volatile versus refractory budget of phosphorus in planet-forming environments have so far eluded empirical characterization. We employ high-resolution spectra from *Hubble Space Telescope* (HST)/Space Telescope Imaging Spectrograph (STIS) in the ultraviolet and the PI230 receiver on the single-dish APEX telescope in the sub-mm to constrain the phosphorus budget in the well-characterized HD 100546 star and protoplanetary disc system. We measure $\log(P/H)_\star = -7.50^{+0.23}_{-0.28}$ on the stellar surface, which traces the total inventory of P in accreting gas and dust from the inner disc. The inner disc gas, inside of the main dust trap, has $\log(P/H)_{\text{in}} \lesssim -8.70$, and the outer disc gas $\log(P/H)_{\text{out}} \lesssim -9.30$. Phosphorus in the disc is carried by a relatively refractory reservoir, consistent with minerals such as apatite or schreibersite, or with ammonium phosphate salts, in terms of sublimation temperature. We discuss the impact this might have on the two protoplanets around HD 100546. Our results contribute to our understanding of the chemical habitability of planetary systems and lay a foundation for future explorations, especially in the context of *JWST* and *Ariel* which can study phosphorus in exoplanet atmospheres.

Key words: astrochemistry – planets and satellites: formation – protoplanetary discs – stars: chemically peculiar – stars: variables: T Tauri, Herbig Ae/Be.

1 INTRODUCTION

How phosphorus (P) arrives in planets, and in what abundance, is of particular importance across astrophysics, Earth, and planetary sciences. The P abundance in the envelopes of giant planets constitutes one of the clues to their formation history (Öberg & Wordsworth 2019). P also has an essential role in biology, in the information-carrying molecules of life (Westheimer 1987), and prebiotic chemistry (as a buffer and reagent; Patel et al. 2015). As the debate around the phosphine detection in Venus’s atmosphere has illustrated (e.g. Greaves et al. 2021; Lincowski et al. 2021; Villanueva et al. 2021), gas-phase P also has potential as a biosignature, albeit this interpretation is critically dependent on the magnitude and chemistry of abiotic exogeneous and endogeneous sources (Sousa-Silva et al. 2020; Bains et al. 2021). The P chemistry of planetary atmospheres and surfaces is therefore a key consideration in the search for life on exoplanets in the era of *JWST*, *Ariel*, and high-resolution ground-based spectroscopy.

P exhibits a diverse behaviour in astrophysical and exoplanetary contexts: it undergoes a journey from its formation in stars, to the diffuse and dense interstellar medium (ISM), to planets that may take it from gas, to solid, and potentially back to gas again, whilst transitioning across a wide range of oxidation states (from -3 to $+5$; e.g. Pasek, Dworkin & Lauretta 2007; Jenkins 2009). This rich chemical behaviour means there is still much to be understood about the distribution and chemistry of P in planetary systems. Developing this understanding is ultimately a foundation to prospecting the Universe for life – P is a key part of chemical habitability (Krijt et al. 2023).

P begins its journey to planets in the ISM, having been synthesized and delivered by dying massive stars. It is usually classed as a (semi)refractory element, locked in solids at equilibrium temperatures ≤ 1229 K (Lodders 2003), but observations of the diffuse atomic ISM indicate that all elemental P is accounted for by *atomic gas* in the most diffuse ISM regions (Jenkins 2009, and references therein). The gas-phase P budget in the molecular ISM is thought to be dominated by three species: phosphorus monoxide PO and mononitride PN, and phosphacetylene HCP (Mininni et al. 2018;

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Chantzos et al. 2020), with the latter being mainly seen around evolved stars. PO and PN are easily synthesized in the gas phase (Thorne et al. 1984; Millar, Bennett & Herbst 1987). Progressive improvements to the phosphorus chemical network yield the same overall conclusion regarding the main gas-phase reservoirs (Adams, McIntosh & Smith 1990; Millar 1991; MacKay & Charnley 2001; Aota & Aikawa 2012; Jiménez-Serra et al. 2018; Chantzos et al. 2020; Sil et al. 2021; Fernández-Ruz, Jiménez-Serra & Aguirre 2023).

Since the first detection of PN in Orion KL and other high-mass star-forming regions (Ziurys 1987), PN, PO, and HCP have been found in various combinations in cold and warm star-forming cores (Fontani et al. 2016; Rivilla et al. 2016; Mininni et al. 2018; Wurmser & Bergner 2022), Galactic Centre clouds (Rivilla et al. 2018), and in outflows from protostars (Yamaguchi et al. 2011; Lefloch et al. 2016; Bergner et al. 2019) and evolved stars (Milam et al. 2008; De Beck et al. 2013). Additionally, HCP and PH₃ have been found in the outflowing envelope around the evolved star IRC+10216 (Agúndez, Cernicharo & Guélin 2007; Agúndez et al. 2008, 2014).

The above observational studies find gas-phase PO, PN, and HCP abundances spanning 3 orders of magnitude: from as low as $X/H_2 = 10^{-10}$ to as high as the solar elemental P/H value 2.5×10^{-7} (Asplund et al. 2009). These values correspond to a range of depletions from strong, factor of 1000 depleted gas-phase elemental P, to undepleted within the uncertainties. The depletion of P from the gas phase is highly environment-dependent, with nearly all elemental P in the gas in the diffuse ISM (Jenkins 2009). Observations of star-forming regions lend support to the importance of sputtering in keeping P-species in the gas phase, because diatomic P-bearing molecules are abundant in outflow-shocked material where solids are collisionally eroded (Mininni et al. 2018; Wurmser & Bergner 2022). In terms of thermal desorption, PO and PN have a desorption energy of $E_B = 1900$ K or 5770 K ($T_{\text{sub}} \approx 35$ K or 125 K; Rivilla et al. 2016; Piacentino & Öberg 2022), placing PO and PN in the domain of (hyper)volatiles. Phosphine (PH₃) may be an important P-bearing ice species, but models suggest that in photon-dominated regions, such as the observable outer layers of protoplanetary discs, any PH₃ released into the gas is photodissociated; the released P then goes on to form PO and PN (Rivilla et al. 2020). There is a lack of gas-phase PN or PO towards hot core environments (e.g. Bernal, Koelemay & Ziurys 2021; Fontani et al. 2024). Hot cores are the centrally irradiated, ‘hot’ ($T_{\text{kin}} \gtrsim 100$ K) inner regions of protostellar cores (Wilson, Downes & Biegging 1979) where volatile ices sublimate (Garrod & Widicus Weaver 2013) and should be detectable in the gas. It is therefore unlikely that grain-phase P is mainly in a volatile ice such as PN, PO, or PH₃. Instead, these molecules are likely formed in the gas after shock sputtering of a semivolatile grain carrier like apatite minerals (Bergner et al. 2022).

Thermodynamic models have shown that P condensation in a disc is highly sensitive to pressure, assumed gas-phase species, and the details of condensation (Sears 1978; Fegley & Lewis 1980). Equilibrium condensation models for early Solar system conditions indicate that P first transfers from the gas into the mineral schreibersite (with a half-mass condensation temperature $T_{50 \text{ per cent}} \sim 1229$ K at solar composition; Lodders 2003), before transforming to phosphate minerals at lower temperatures ($T < 800$ K; Pasek 2019).

Whilst in the Solar system we have a record of the P-bearing condensation products and their altered forms in the form of primitive CI chondrites containing schreibersite and apatite (e.g. Morlok et al. 2006), the poorly known initial conditions and chemical evolution

of discs and planetesimals mean these only give us a partial insight into how P generally behaves in planet-forming environments. Our new observations of P in a planet-forming disc and its accretion-dominated host star will fill this gap, and directly probe its gas-solid phase partitioning.

Stars earlier than type F5 ($M_* \gtrsim 1.4 M_{\odot}$) do not have deep convective mixing in their envelope, rather being dominated by rotational mixing and diffusion (Turcotte 2002). This allows accretion from a protoplanetary disc to ‘contaminate’ the observable photosphere (Jermyn & Kama 2018). The abundance of dust-forming elements has been shown to be low on the surface of Herbig Ae/Be stars that have strong dust traps (visible as bright dust rings) in their discs, the so-called ‘transitional discs’ (Kama, Folsom & Pinilla 2015; Guzmán-Díaz et al. 2023). The presence of a strong dust trap removes refractory elements from the accretion stream, and this provides a diagnostic method to measure the refractory fraction of volatile and semivolatile elements. We have previously used this method to determine the refractory fraction of sulfur (89 ± 8 per cent locked in refractory solids; Kama et al. 2019).

The depletion behaviour of P from the gas phase is not yet fully understood, so observations of P-carriers in physically well-characterized environments are needed to more accurately model its partitioning between specific gas- and solid-phase species before, and during, planet formation. In this paper, we apply the stellar accretion contamination method for the first empirical study of the major P carriers in a protoplanetary disc. This specifies the target selection criteria: an intermediate-mass young star with a transitional protoplanetary disc, both with well-characterized bulk parameters and as much information on chemical abundances as possible.

2 THE HD 100 546 SYSTEM

The Herbig Ae/Be system HD 100546 consists of a well-characterized A0-type star ($2.4 M_{\odot}$) surrounded by a warm, flaring transitional disc. The large grains in the disc are trapped in an inner (22 to 40 au) and outer (150 to 230 au) dust ring. The outer dust gap and inner cavity each host a protoplanet candidate: HD 100546 b ($a_{\text{maj,b}} = 143$ au, $M_b = 3 M_{\text{Jup}}$) and c ($a_{\text{maj,b}} = 13$ au, $M_b = 8 M_{\text{Jup}}$; Pinilla, Birnstiel & Walsh 2015; Pyerin et al. 2021). There is a significant literature on the source, we direct the reader to Benisty et al. (2010), Panić et al. (2010), Bruderer et al. (2012), Quanz et al. (2013), Walsh et al. (2014), Pinilla et al. (2015), Kama et al. (2016), Booth et al. (2021, 2024), and Keyte et al. (2023, 2024) as a starting point. The physical and chemical structure of the disc has been modelled in detail, reproducing observed rotational line emission from the main carbon-, oxygen-, and sulphur-carrying species. The temperature structure of the disc is such that the direct freeze-out of gas-phase hypervolatiles (e.g. CO) in the disc is negligible (Bruderer et al. 2012; Kama et al. 2016; Panić & Min 2017). The total volatile elemental C and O are not substantially depleted from the gas phase (Bruderer et al. 2012; Kama et al. 2016), while sulphur is depleted by a factor ~ 1000 with large radial variation (Keyte et al. 2023, 2024). The gas-phase abundances of C, O, and S vary radially and azimuthally (Keyte et al. 2023, 2024), implying the chemical composition of material available to accrete may differ for the two protoplanets.

3 OBSERVATIONS

To determine the budget of refractory and volatile P carriers in the planet-forming disc around HD 100546 (see Section 2), we study emission in rotational transitions of P-bearing molecules (PO, PN,

Table 1. APEX submm spectroscopic observations of HD 100546.

Date yyyy-mm-dd	ν_{LO} (GHz)	t_{exp} (h)	PWV (mm) range
2018-07-30	234	2.4	0.9...1.2
	234, 242	3.6	1.2...1.6
2018-07-31	234, 242	4.8	1.0...2.2
2018-08-03	242	2.8	1.6...1.9
2018-11-06	242	2.5	1.2...1.4
2018-08-08	242	3.9	2.6...2.9
2018-11-07	234, 242	2.8	0.8...1.6
2018-11-12	234	4.2	3.2...3.9

Note. The columns give the date (1), local oscillator frequency setting ν_{LO} (2), on-source exposure time (3), and precipitable water column (4). Grouped LO settings were observed in the same observing window on a given night.

Table 2. PO, PN, and HCP rotational transitions observed with APEX.

Mol.	Transition	ν_{ul} (GHz)	RMS (mK)	$T_{\text{A}} dv$ (mK $\frac{\text{km}}{\text{s}}$)
PN	$J = 5-4$	234.936	2.8	<13.2
HCP	$J = 6-5$	239.694	2.8	<26.4
PO	$J = \frac{11}{2}-\frac{9}{2}, F = 6-5, l = e$	239.949	2.8	<26.4
PO	$J = \frac{11}{2}-\frac{9}{2}, F = 5-4, l = e$	239.958	2.8	<26.4
PO	$J = \frac{11}{2}-\frac{9}{2}, F = 6-5, l = f$	240.141	2.5	<23.7
PO	$J = \frac{11}{2}-\frac{9}{2}, F = 5-4, l = f$	240.153	2.6	<24.6

Note. Upper limits are given with 3σ confidence. The HCP line was not included in the modelling.

and HCP) in the disc gas and atomic absorption lines of P ionization states in the photosphere of the central star.

3.1 HST/STIS

To determine the stellar photospheric P abundance, we used archival spectra from the Space Telescope Imaging Spectrograph (STIS) on *Hubble Space Telescope* (HST). The high-resolution ($R \approx 114\,000$) data covered wavelengths from 1150 to 2887 Å and was downloaded from the StarCAT catalogue (see Data Availability section). Two spectra of the star were available, taken on 2000 July 22 and 2000 November 04, with signal-to-noise $\text{SNR} \approx 10$ and ≈ 30 , respectively, at ≈ 1500 Å. We used the spectrum with the higher SNR.

The use of the HST/STIS spectrum to derive the stellar P/H ratio for HD 100546 is described in Section 4.1.

3.2 APEX

To study molecular emission lines of P-bearing species in the protoplanetary disc, observations of PO and PN rotational lines were carried out with the PI230 receiver and FFTS-4G backend on the APEX submillimetre telescope in 2018 (proposal E-0102.C-0927A). Two local oscillator settings were used: $\nu_{\text{LO}} = 234$ GHz for a set of PO and HCP lines and $\nu_{\text{LO}} = 242$ GHz for PN. A summary of the submillimetre observations is given in Table 1 and the covered transitions are listed in Table 2.

The APEX data underwent standard reduction procedures at ESO. After applying minor, low-order baseline corrections, we did not detect any of the targeted lines. The observing settings were chosen in such a way as to ensure that even upper limits would provide useful constraints on the gas-phase phosphorus budget, which we discuss in Section 4.2.

4 ANALYSIS

We investigate the phosphorus budget in the HD 100546 system by measuring its abundance relative to hydrogen on the stellar surface and in the disc gas. With the stellar surface measurement, we constrain the total amount of P passing through the last major dust trap and accreting on to the star; while, with the disc gas measurement, we constrain the fraction of elemental P locked in either dust grains or mid-plane ices.

As a reference value, we adopt the solar abundance of P, $\log(P/H)_{\odot} = -6.59 \pm 0.03$ (Asplund et al. 2009). An alternative would be the proto-solar value, but estimates differ significantly: Lodders (2003) estimated $\log(P/H)_{\odot}^{\text{prot}} = -6.46 \pm 0.04$, while Asplund, Amarsi & Grevesse (2021) suggest $\log(P/H)_{\odot}^{\text{prot}} = -6.526$. We use the current solar abundance to place constraints on the unseen solid component. The abundances are conventionally expressed as the base-10 logarithm of the elemental number ratio $\log(P/H)_{\star}$ for stellar photospheres, and as the absolute ratio for disc gas.

The disc around HD 100546 includes a bright inner dust ring from 22 to 40 au, and a faint outer ring from 150 to 230 au. We can assume a fraction δ_{L} of the inward-moving dust mass is trapped as large grains in the inner ring dust trap. This removes a corresponding fraction of the refractory component of each chemical element from each parcel of disc material. Thus, if 100 per cent of Fe in a parcel of disc material is contained in refractory dust, then $100 \times (1 - \delta_{\text{L}})$ per cent of all Fe would pass through the main dust trap and accrete on to the star, where it can be observed in the stellar photospheric composition as long as the mixing is slow and the accretion rate is high enough (Turcotte 2002; Jermyn & Kama 2018). This method allows to infer the fraction of each chemical element locked in solid particles. We apply it below to P.

The high disc accretion rate on to HD 100546, $\log(\dot{M}_{\text{acc}}) = -7.04_{-0.15}^{+0.13} M_{\odot} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ (Fairlamb et al. 2015), leads the photospheric mixing fraction of freshly accreted material to be $f_{\text{acc}} = 98$ per cent, using a stellar mixing model that includes rotation, diffusion, and other processes (Jermyn & Kama 2022). The stellar photospheric composition is thus, to a high degree of accuracy, the elemental composition of the disc material currently accreting on to the star.

4.1 The accreted stellar phosphorus abundance

To measure the stellar photospheric P/H ratio, we adopted stellar parameters and known photospheric abundances for HD 100546 from Kama et al. (2016), who followed the spectral synthesis and fitting methodology of Folsom et al. (2012). The 2016 analysis did not include P due to a lack of suitable lines in the ESO Fiber-fed Extended Range Optical Spectrograph (FEROS) data. This is not unusual: because of a lack of suitable lines, the phosphorus abundance is rarely measured in intermediate-mass stars. Lines of P are however present in the HST/STIS spectrum we used. In our analysis of the STIS data, we employ the Zeeman spectral synthesis code (Landstreet 1988, 2011; Wade et al. 2001; Folsom et al. 2012), ATLAS9 model atmospheres (Kurucz 1993; Castelli & Kurucz 2003) and a linelist from the Vienna Atomic Line Database (VALD; Piskunov et al. 1995; Ryabchikova et al. 1997, 2015; Kupka et al. 1999, 2000).

The lines in the STIS ultraviolet (UV) spectrum of HD 100546 are mostly blended due to crowding and rotational broadening ($v \sin(i) \approx 65 \text{ km s}^{-1}$). Our analysis of the weak P lines between 1301 and 1787 Å is further complicated by the low SNR and by inaccuracies in UV line parameters. Based on a visual inspection of the spectrum, we chose a small wavelength region from 1542.8 to 1543.5 Å, dominated by two P lines, as shown in the top panel of

Figure 1. **Top panel:** the stellar spectrum of HD 100546 is in light grey, the binned spectrum is in dark grey, the three smooth curves are the best-fitting synthetic spectrum and its $\pm 3\sigma$ parameter deviations. The highlighted spectral region is used for estimating $\log(P/H)_*$ using the chi-square minimization. **Bottom panel:** χ^2 as a function of $\log(P/H)_*$. The solid vertical line indicates the minimum and the adjacent dashed lines are $\pm 3\sigma$ confidence intervals. The solar and proto-solar values are shown for comparison.

Fig. 1. The stronger absorption feature at ≈ 1542.5 Å is a blend of a P II line with an equally strong carbon and slightly weaker silicon line. Our model of the strong P II feature likely suffers from errors in the C I and Si I line modelling. Adopting C/H and Si/H values from Kama et al. (2016), we find the stronger P II absorption feature is too deep to be explained by an excess of phosphorus abundance. This is because the excess phosphorus leads to a significant overprediction of the weaker P I/P II line.

The accuracy of oscillator strengths is a concern in particular when analysing UV spectra. The weaker absorption feature is a blend of a singly ionized P II line at ≈ 1543.133 Å a neutral P I line at ≈ 1543.288 Å a Mn II line, and three Fe II lines. We tested the effect of the statistically weighted oscillator strength, $\log(g_l f_{lu})$, of the P and Fe lines, and found that P II dominates the weak feature. The $\log(g_l f_{lu})$ values of the P II and P I lines reported in the

VALD database are -2.295 (Kurucz 2012) and -0.820 (Kurucz & Peytremann 1975), respectively.

To determine the stellar photospheric phosphorus abundance, $\log(P/H)_*$, for HD 100546, we estimated the $\log(g_l f_{lu})$ value for the P II line at ≈ 1543.133 Å by a χ^2 -minimization fitting of the *HST*/STIS spectrum of Vega with stellar parameters and photospheric abundances from Fitzpatrick (2010). This author determined $\log(P/H)_*$ for Vega using an International Ultraviolet Explorer (IUE) spectrum with 78 lines of phosphorus. From our analysis of Vega, we obtained $\log(g_l f_{lu}) = -2.224$ for the P II line at ≈ 1543.133 Å. We adopted this for our analysis of HD 100546.

Using χ^2 minimisation on a continuum-normalised spectrum, we find the stellar photospheric phosphorus abundance in HD 100546 to be $\log(P/H)_* = -7.50^{+0.23}_{-0.28}$ (3σ confidence; see Fig. 1, right-hand panel). This result is validated with a fit on a second spectral region, which yields a $\log(P/H)_*$ value within 1σ of the above result (see Appendix B).

4.1.1 Stellar parameters for the disc model

We use the absolute stellar spectrum constructed by Bruderer et al. (2012) using dereddened FUSE and IUE observations at UV wavelengths, and extended to longer wavelengths using the B9V template of Pickles (1998). The stellar luminosity is $36 L_\odot$ (Kama et al. 2016). The X-ray spectrum was characterized as a thermal spectrum with a temperature of 7×10^7 K from 1 to 100 keV, with a luminosity of $L_x = 7.94 \times 10^{28}$ erg s^{-1} .

4.2 Phosphorus in the protoplanetary disc gas

Next, we analyse the APEX data described Section 3.2 to constrain the total gas-phase elemental P abundance in the HD 100546 disc. We ran source-specific models using the 2D thermochemical code DALI (Bruderer et al. 2012; Bruderer 2013). Using an input stellar spectrum (Bruderer et al. 2012) and a 2D physical disc structure, the code iterates between continuum Monte Carlo radiative transfer and a chemistry solver to converge on the thermal and chemical structure of the disc, which allows to model outputs such as molecular lines. The disc structure we use for everything except the distribution of phosphorus species, is based on the HD 100546 disc model consecutively improved by Bruderer et al. (2012), Kama et al. (2016), and Keyte et al. (2023, 2024). Below, we briefly restate some of the key features of the model. The adopted DALI model parameters are listed in Table A1.

The disc structure is parametrized, with a surface density that follows the standard form of a power law with an exponential taper:

$$\Sigma_{\text{gas}} = \Sigma_c \left(\frac{r}{R_c} \right)^{-\gamma} \exp \left[- \left(\frac{r}{R_c} \right)^{2-\gamma} \right], \quad (1)$$

where r is the radius, γ is the surface density exponent, and the reference surface density at R_c is Σ_c/e . The dust surface density is $\Sigma_{\text{gas}}/\Delta_{g/d}$, where $\Delta_{g/d}$ is the gas-to-dust mass ratio. The vertical distribution of gas follows a Gaussian with scale height:

$$h(r) = h_c \left(\frac{r}{R_c} \right)^\psi, \quad (2)$$

where h_c is the scale height at R_c , and the power-law index of the scale height, ψ , describes the flaring of the disc.

Σ_{gas} and Σ_{dust} extend from the dust sublimation radius ($R_{\text{sub}} = 0.25$ au) to the edge of the disc ($R_{\text{out}} = 500$ au), and can be varied independently inside the cavity radius R_{cav} with the multiplication factors δ_{gas} and δ_{dust} .

Dust settling is implemented by considering two different populations of grains: small grains (0.005–1 μm) and large grains (0.005–1 mm). The vertical density structure of the dust is such that large grains are settled towards the mid-plane, prescribed by the settling parameter, χ ¹:

$$\rho_{\text{dust, large}} = \frac{f \Sigma_{\text{dust}}}{\sqrt{2\pi} r \chi h} \exp \left[-\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\pi/2 - \theta}{\chi h} \right)^2 \right] \quad (3)$$

$$\rho_{\text{dust, small}} = \frac{(1-f) \Sigma_{\text{dust}}}{\sqrt{2\pi} r h} \exp \left[-\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\pi/2 - \theta}{h} \right)^2 \right], \quad (4)$$

where f is the mass fraction of large grains and θ is the opening angle from the mid-plane as viewed from the central star. Both grain populations follow a size distribution prescribed by a power law with index $q = -3.5$.

4.2.1 Chemical network

The chemical reaction network used in our model is based on a subset of the UMIST 06² database for astrochemistry (Woodall et al. 2007). It consists of 145 species (including neutral and charged polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons – PAHs) and 1814 individual reactions. The DALI code includes H₂ formation on dust, freeze-out, thermal desorption, hydrogenation, gas-phase reactions, photodissociation and ionization, X-ray induced processes, cosmic-ray induced reactions, PAH/small grain charge exchange/hydrogenation, and reactions with vibrationally excited H₂. Non-thermal desorption is only included for a small number of species (CO, CO₂, H₂O, CH₄, NH₃). For grain surface chemistry, only hydrogenation of simple species is considered (C, CH, CH₂, CH₃, N, NH, NH₂, O, OH). The details of these processes are described in Bruderer et al. (2012). For this study, we have updated the network with 26 P-bearing species and 135 reactions from UMIST. Binding energies for all P-bearing species are set to $E_B = 5770$ K following the values determined for PO and PN by Piacentino & Öberg (2022), equivalent to a sublimation temperature of $T \approx 125$ K. The elemental abundances used in our model are listed in Table A2.

4.2.2 Molecular excitation and transition data

We adopted data for PO and PN rotational energy levels and transitions from the LAMDA database (Schöier et al. 2005; Toboła et al. 2007; Lique et al. 2018). Some necessary corrections to the energy level ordering were made by J.Bergner.

4.2.3 Gas-phase elemental P/H in the disc

To constrain the *volatile* elemental phosphorus abundance in the disc, we used a two-stage modelling approach:

First, to get a rough estimate of the global depletion of gas-phase P, we modelled the disc-integrated PO and PN line flux upper limits using a constant volatile P/H ratio across the whole disc. Representative gas-phase PO and PN number abundance maps can be seen in Fig. 2. The modelled line fluxes, with volatile elemental P values from $P/H = 10^{-12}$ to 10^{-6} (solar-like), are shown in Fig. 3. The

¹Note that the dust settling parameter χ is distinct from the χ^2 statistic used elsewhere in this paper.

²UMIST stands for the former University of Manchester Institute of Science and Technology, numbers are added to the network version by the last digits of the publication year.

Figure 2. PO and PN abundance maps from our DALI model assuming a global volatile phosphorus abundance $P/H = 10^{-9}$. The white contours enclose 50 per cent and 75 per cent of total line flux for the PN 234.936 GHz transition.

Figure 3. Volatile elemental P/H in the HD 100546 disc assuming a globally constant abundance. Disc-integrated 3σ line flux upper limits for the PO and PN transitions observed with APEX (black lines), and predicted line fluxes for a DALI model grid covering volatile elemental phosphorus abundances from $P/H = 10^{-12}$ to 10^{-6} (circles from bottom to top show 1 dex steps in P/H) are shown.

PO lines provided a weak constraint on the volatile P: $P/H \lesssim 10^{-6}$, which is an order of magnitude higher than the solar value. Our globally constant total elemental gas-phase P/H is based on the PN 6–5 line, from which we find $(P/H)_{\text{global}} \lesssim 5 \times 10^{-10}$.

Secondly – and this is our final, best-fitting model – we modelled the data by dividing the disc into two radial zones with an independent gas-phase P/H ratio: one for material inside the inner edge of the main

Figure 4. Coupled constraints on the gas-phase elemental P/H ratio inside (P/H_{in} , x -axis) and outside (P/H_{out} , y -axis) the 22 au dust cavity in the HD 100546 disc. Allowed abundance sets (points in the bottom left area up to the dotted curve) meet the constraint from the PN line disc-integrated 3σ flux upper limit (dotted curve). Excluded abundance sets (points to the top and right of the dotted curve) are ruled out by our data. The inner cavity P/H value is compared with the ratio as measured on the star for the accreting material, $(P/H)_*$, and the solar (Asplund et al. 2009) and proto-solar (Lodders 2003) values.

dust ring (i.e. inside the 22 au dust cavity; P/H_{in}), and another for the outer disc (P/H_{out}). This two-zone model was motivated by the abrupt change in temperature near the edge of the large dust cavity, with the temperature reaching ≈ 180 K at the inner edge of the dust ring (Keyte et al. 2023); and by the assumption that inward-drifting pebbles would stop in the dust ring and release their volatile ices. The results are shown in Fig. 4 and show that a useful set of upper limits, described by a surface in the $(P/H)_{\text{in}}, (P/H)_{\text{out}}$ coordinate space, can be obtained. Looking at the extreme values for both axes, we independently constrain the gas-phase total P/H ratio inside the dust ring to be $P/H_{\text{in}} \lesssim 2 \times 10^{-9}$, while outside the dust ring we find $P/H_{\text{out}} \lesssim 5 \times 10^{-10}$.

Since the two protoplanet candidates are located inside (planet c) and outside (planet b) the main dust ring, the P/H_{in} and P/H_{out} limits can, respectively, be associated with gas currently being accreted by the protoplanets.

5 DISCUSSION

We have identified that, in the HD 100546 system, the total elemental gas-phase P abundance is depleted inside the main dust ring by a factor ≥ 129 and outside this zone by a factor ≥ 513 (obtained assuming a solar reference abundance and dividing that by the inner and outer disc upper limits from Section 4.2). We also find that the total (gas *plus* solid) elemental P is depleted in the dust-depleted disc material accreting on to the star by a factor ≈ 8 (obtained from dividing the solar reference by the $\log(P/H)_*$ from Section 4.1). These results provide independent insights into the behaviour of P in the HD 100546 system, which we discuss below.

5.1 Phosphorus volatility in the HD 100546 disc

The factor of 8 depletion of P on the stellar surface, identified above (see Section 4.1), is consistent with the factor of ~ 10 overall

depletion of refractory elements on the stellar surface (Kama et al. 2016).

In addition to a factor of ≈ 8 depletion of P, the accretion-dominated photosphere of the star HD 100546 is depleted in other refractory elements, also by approximately a factor of 10 (e.g. Mg, Ca, Si, Al; see appendix A in Kama et al. 2016). This is despite the disc itself having an overall a gas-to-dust ratio of $\Delta_{\text{gd}} = 10$ –100 (e.g. Bruderer et al. 2012; Kama et al. 2016). Together, these observations imply that approximately 90 per cent of the inward-moving dust mass from the outer disc does not currently reach the star.

The most significant finding from the two-zone disc model is that the total gas-phase P abundance in the inner cavity is $P/H_{\text{in}} < 2 \times 10^{-9}$, which is at least 16 times less than the abundance on the stellar photosphere. We identify the stellar P/H_* value with the total gas *plus* solid abundance of P in the inner cavity. In other words, P/H_* represents any and all carriers of P that are carried past the main dust ring and through the inner cavity. Given the large difference between P/H_* and P/H_{in} , the two-zone disc model strongly suggests that most of the P passing through the dust cavity is contained in small dust grains, hidden from the gas-phase chemistry probed by our APEX observations.

The values of P/H_{star} and P/H_{in} are thus consistent with a scenario where most of the inward-moving dust mass has gotten trapped, most likely in the prominent dust ring at 22 to 40 au, leaving the inner cavity deprived of large dust grains (pebbles) and the stellar surface deprived of dust-forming elements. Only small dust grains, which are coupled to the gas but generally constitute a small fraction of the total dust mass, can traverse the inner cavity. In the HD 100546 disc model from Keyte et al. (2024), grains ≤ 1 mm in size constitute 5 per cent of the dust mass, which given the various uncertainties involved appears consistent with ≈ 10 per cent of refractories reaching the stellar surface. This general finding on refractories being depleted on the star due to dust trapping is in line with our previous work in Kama

Figure 5. The dominant phosphorous reservoirs throughout the HD 100546 disc. *Left-hand panel:* a map of the calculated disc temperature structure, which dictates phosphorous mineral stability. Normalized height above mid-plane is given by z/r , with height above mid-plane, z (au), divided by the radial distance, r (au). Hatched regions indicate the two dust rings identified in this system and the dotted black line marks the water iceline (parametrized simply as the 121 K isotherm after Lodders 2003). *Right-hand panel:* a map of the dominant phosphorous reservoirs in the disc assuming equilibrium at the dust temperature. The minerals apatite, merrillite, and schreibersite progressively replace each other as the main phosphorous reservoir as temperature is increased, up to the point where temperatures are high enough that all major phosphorous-bearing mineral phases have sublimated and most phosphorous is in the gas phase. Phosphorous dissolved in Fe metal is never a dominant reservoir, but its presence is mapped by the dashed contour. Mineral stabilities were taken from Pasek (2019).

et al. (2016, 2019). The stellar and inner disc P/H values furthermore lead to the conclusion that the dominant phosphorus reservoir in the HD 100546 disc is sufficiently refractory to remain solid at the inner edge of the main dust belt, where the temperature reaches nearly 200 K.

We are here using ‘refractory’ more broadly compared to its cosmochemical meaning, and use it to refer to anything less volatile than water ice. This distinction is made on the basis that the stellar oxygen abundance is normal, i.e. undepleted, in HD 100546 and other Herbig Ae/Be stars with dust-poor accretion. This constant O/H value regardless of whether the disc is transitional or full, is taken as evidence that H₂O ice, which is the dominant carrier of elemental O in discs, generally sublimates in the main dust trap in such transitional discs and freely accretes on to the star (Kama et al. 2019). Ice sublimation is in general more likely at the inner edge of dust traps, as temperatures rise due to increased illumination (Broome et al. 2023; Chen et al. 2024). In the case of HD 100546, the lack of oxygen depletion is consistent with the matching locations of the water iceline and inner dust ring (Keyte et al. 2023, 2024; see also Fig. 5).

We note that while the volatility trend of elemental depletions on the surface of accreting Herbig Ae/Be stars is consistent from the most volatile elements (C), through the intermediates (Na, S, Zn), to the most refractory ones (e.g. Fe, Ti), oxygen does not follow this trend (Kama et al. 2015, 2019). Instead, in material accreting on to Herbig Ae/Be stars oxygen has a refractory fraction of 0 ± 2 per cent (Kama et al. 2015). This may be due to disc or stellar evolution processes, or systematics in the oxygen abundance measurements and is being investigated in a separate study. While this raises doubts as to the overall reliability of the oxygen abundance, we argue that the effect is likely mainly relevant for masking the minor refractory component of O. If H₂O ice, the expected major O carrier, was being trapped in the last major dust trap, the star would be receiving strongly oxygen-depleted material, which would then show a depletion signature of comparable magnitude to Fe or Ti.

This finding of elemental P being locked almost exclusively in dust is consistent with the temperature at the location of the dust trap,

which predicts that – at equilibrium, which is a limiting assumption – most P at this location would be in refractory mineral form as apatite (Fig. 5). We only include the equilibrium composition as a secondary argument, to suggest that our findings are not inconsistent with the P reservoirs expected in case the composition had time to equilibrate in the dust trap. Apatite or large P oxides (e.g. P₄O₁₀) with similar volatility were also inferred to be likely grain-phase carriers of P in the protostellar stage (Bergner et al. 2022).

5.2 The main phosphorus reservoir

The conclusion from above is that most, or all, elemental P is locked in refractory solids. This solid P is most likely trapped in pebbles in the 22–40 au dust ring, similar to even more refractory elements such as iron, titanium, or aluminium. The accreted oxygen abundance on the HD 100546 stellar photosphere is consistent with almost no depletion, indicating almost all oxygen passes freely through the dust trap. If we assume the elemental O budget is dominated by H₂O, we can conclude the main reservoir of elemental phosphorus in the HD 100546 disc is more refractory than H₂O ice, so that it can remain trapped while H₂O ice sublimates. The temperature of the dust trap is ≈ 70 K (outer edge) to ≈ 180 K (inner edge), sufficient to sublimate water (Kama et al. 2016; Keyte et al. 2023).

Our empirical finding that almost all P is locked in solids that are more refractory than water ice is consistent with predictions from thermochemical equilibrium. As seen in Fig. 5, we find that the preferred equilibrium reservoir is a mineral phase in much of the disc, and specifically in the inner dust ring. Equilibrium condensation sequence calculations place P in the refractory minerals schreibersite, apatite, or merrillite (Fegley & Lewis 1980; Lodders 2003; Pirim et al. 2014; Pasek 2019). We note that it is unclear whether thermochemical equilibrium is an appropriate assumption for the material in the HD 100546 dust ring.

Among meteorites, the main P reservoir in hydrous carbonaceous chondrites and ordinary chondrites is phosphates, such as apatite (≥ 90 per cent of total elemental P), or schreibersite (≤ 10 per cent; Pasek & Lauretta 2008, and references therein). However, the

Figure 6. Sketch of the HD 100546 system with the star, disc, and two claimed protoplanets. Volatiles that evaporate in the inner dust trap accrete along with hydrogen gas and small grains. The stellar photosphere is accretion-dominated, and its composition thus represents the sum of small grains and volatiles.

Rosetta mission to comet 67P/Churyumov–Gerasimenko found no evidence for apatite and only weak consistency with schreibersite for the main P carrier in the cometary dust grains (Gardner et al. 2020). In samples from asteroid Ryugu, the main P-bearing phases were found to be apatite, schreibersite, and a new phase: hydrated ammonium–magnesium phosphorus (HAMP) grains (Pilorget et al. 2024). A similar list of P-carriers has been found in samples from asteroid Bennu (Lauretta et al. 2024).

Ammonium salts, such as the ammonium phosphate found recently on Ryugu (see above), have become a contender for carrying a significant fraction of nitrogen, sulphur, or other elements such as halogens in a semirefractory reservoir, sublimating at a few hundred kelvins, based on Solar system evidence (Altwegg et al. 2020, 2022; Poch et al. 2020). While we cannot rule out ammonium phosphate (NH_4PO_4) as the main carrier of P in the HD 100546 disc, we also have no evidence for a significant total mass of diverse ammonium salts being withheld in the dust trap. This is because the accreted photospheric N/H ratio of HD 100546, $\log(N/H)_* = -3.82 \pm 0.30$ (Kama et al. 2016), is marginally supersolar, assuming $\log(N/H)_\odot = -4.17 \pm 0.05$ (Asplund et al. 2009). Thus, we have no evidence for nitrogen depletion in the accretion stream.

On the other hand, the small fraction of elemental N needed to lock away only P atoms in ammonium phosphate would be too small to cause a measurable N depletion on the star ($3 \times P/N \approx 1$ per cent for solar abundances) so we cannot rule it out. However, the lack of evidence of trapping of more abundant salt species in the dust trap then demands a very specific explanation. If ammonium phosphate were an important P reservoir, a mechanism strongly favouring its formation over NH_4^+ salts with a more abundant anion (such as sulphate) would be required to explain the lack of measurable elemental N depletion in the HD 100546 stellar photosphere.

Our available evidence therefore favours a mineral reservoir, such as apatite or schreibersite, to account for most of the P. Ammonium phosphate is also a candidate, but it may not have a dominant role as we do not see a depletion of N that would indicate the presence of large amounts of diverse ammonium salts as a ‘volatile vault’ in the dust belt where P is getting trapped.

5.3 The phosphorus budget of the protoplanets

As described in Section 2, the disc around HD 100546 is known to host at least two giant protoplanet candidates: HD 100546 b ($a_{\text{maj,b}} = 143$ au, $M_b = 3 M_{\text{Jup}}$) and c ($a_{\text{maj,b}} = 13$ au, $M_b = 8 M_{\text{Jup}}$) (Pinilla et al. 2015; Pyerin et al. 2021). We illustrate the scenario for HD 100546 in Fig. 6. Protoplanet b orbits in a wide dust gap radially

outwards from the main dust trap (ring), while c orbits inwards of the trap (Walsh et al. 2014; Pinilla et al. 2015).

Our measurements above show that elemental P in the inner few tens of au of this disc can be accounted for entirely by a refractory reservoir: the depletion of P from the gas follows that of Fe, Mg, Si, and other refractories (see also Kama et al. 2015). In an imaginary parcel of homogeneously mixed disc material, almost all P would be contained in dust grains. Most of the dust mass is in large dust grains (pebbles) and thus settled on the mid-plane, where such large grains will drift into dust traps such as the main dust ring. A smaller fraction of total elemental P will be in small grains, which are kinematically coupled to the gas and not as sensitive to trapping in local gas pressure maxima.

The above implies the current availability of P may be very different for the protoplanets b and c. A giant planet may accrete material into its gas envelope either across the disc mid-plane, or through the surface via meridional flows (Teague, Bae & Bergin 2019; Szulágyi, Binkert & Surville 2022). As both planets have opened dust gaps, any currently ongoing mid-plane accretion would be dust-poor as large grains would not be able to accrete. Furthermore, we can hypothesize the inner planet (c) might be accreting particularly low-metallicity material as any solids would need to have first passed through *two* radial dust traps, with the inner trap apparently being the stronger of the two. If this is the case, planet c may end up with a lower metallicity, and a lower total elemental P/H ratio in its envelope compared to the outer planet, b.

If meridional flows dominate the currently ongoing accretion on to either of the planets, that planet (or both) would have a low envelope metallicity, with a correspondingly low elemental P/H ratio.

6 CONCLUSIONS

(i) We find a P abundance $\log(P/H)_* = -7.50^{+0.23}_{-0.28}$ in the stellar photosphere. This is significantly below the solar value, $\log(P/H)_\odot = -6.59 \pm 0.03$. The slowly mixing radiative envelope of the star and the high disc accretion rate imply the $(P/H)_*$ value characterizes the total P/H in the inner disc, where the accretion originates, and not the bulk of the star.

(ii) We find the total gas-phase elemental P abundance in the inner disc, inside the main dust ring, to be $(P/H)_{\text{in}} \lesssim 2 \times 10^{-9}$. We constrain the value outside the dust ring to be $(P/H)_{\text{out}} \lesssim 5 \times 10^{-10}$. These two values characterize P/H in the gas currently being accreted by protoplanet candidates c and b, respectively.

(iii) P in the HD 100546 disc is strongly depleted from the gas into a refractory (dusty) reservoir. This is based on the above conclusions

that P is strongly depleted from the disc gas everywhere, and depleted – but less severely – in the material (gas+dust) in the accretion stream. The main carrier of P in the inner cavity is predicted to be small dust grains that are not trapped in the dust ring at 22 to 40 au.

(iv) Apatite and schreibersite are favoured over volatile ices or ammonium salts as the dominant P reservoir in the grains, both on sublimation temperature grounds and on the grounds that we see the volatiles N, C, and O behaving differently from P in the inner disc.

(v) Our empirical finding that elemental P in the HD 100546 disc is carried entirely, or almost entirely, by dust suggests that the P/H ratio in giant planet envelopes traces their refractory element accretion history as well or even better than sulphur.

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DATA AVAILABILITY

The submillimetre spectroscopic observations of rotational lines of PO, PN, and HCP can be accessed on the APEX data archive,³ under the proposal code 0102.C-0927(A). The *Hubble Space Telescope* spectra are available through the StarCAT⁴ database (Ayres 2010). Our disc model is available on request from the authors.

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APPENDIX A: DISC MODEL PARAMETERS

In Table A1, we list the DALI model parameters adopted for the HD 100546 disc model. The elemental abundances assumed for elements other than P are listed in Table A2.

Table A1. DALI disc model parameters for HD 100546 (Keyte et al. 2023). See also Bruderer et al. (2012) and Kama et al. (2016).

Parameter	Description	Fiducial
R_{sub}	Sublimation radius	0.25 au
R_{gap}	Inner disc size	1.0 au
R_{cav}	Cavity radius	22 au
R_{out}	Disc outer radius	1000 au
R_c	Critical radius for surface density	50 au
δ_{gas}	Gas depletion factor inside cavity	10^{-5}
δ_{dust}	Dust depletion factor inside cavity	10^{-4}
γ	Surface density power law index	1.0
χ	Dust settling parameter	0.2
f	Large-to-small dust mixing	0.95
Σ_c	Σ_{gas} at R_c	87.25 g cm^{-2}
h_c	Scale height at R_c	0.10
ψ	Power-law index of scale height	0.25
$\Delta_{\text{g/d}}$	Gas-to-dust mass ratio	100
L_*	Stellar luminosity	$36 L_{\odot}$
L_X	Stellar X-ray luminosity	$7.94 \times 10^{28} \text{ erg s}^{-1}$
T_X	X-ray plasma temperature	$7.0 \times 10^7 \text{ K}$
ζ_{cr}	Cosmic ray ionization rate	$3.0 \times 10^{-17} \text{ s}^{-1}$
M_{gas}	Disc gas mass	$9.89 \times 10^{-2} M_{\odot}$
M_{dust}	Disc dust mass	$1.06 \times 10^{-3} M_{\odot}$
t_{chem}	Chemical time-scale	5 Myr

Table A2. Chemical element number abundances, relative to H nuclei, in the DALI model of the disc around HD 100546.

Species	n_i/n_{H}
	<i>Fixed</i>
H	1.0
He	9.0×10^{-2}
C	1.5×10^{-5}
N	6.2×10^{-5}
O	3.0×10^{-5}
S	1.0×10^{-8}
Mg	5.0×10^{-7}
Si	5.0×10^{-7}
Fe	5.0×10^{-7}

APPENDIX B: $(P/H)_*$ FROM A SECOND SPECTRAL REGION

We also estimated the P abundance from the P II line between 1535.4 and 1536.4 Å. The P II line is blended with one S II and one Mn II line. No prior abundance measurement for Mn was available from Folsom et al. (2012), so we measured it from the following spectral regions: 1857.52–1859.13 Å, 1863.57–1865.29 Å, 1865.29–1870.33 Å, 1910.00–1912.00 Å, 1942.90–1945.95 Å, and 1916.70–1922.00 Å. We find $(Mn/H)_* = -7.56 \pm 0.35$. We applied this value to estimate $(P/H)_*$ from the spectral region highlighted in Fig. B1. By comparing with the Vega spectrum, we estimated the statistically weighted oscillator strength value for the P II line at 1535.9225 Å to be $\log(g_l f_{lu}) = -1.470$. The value for the P II line reported in VALD is $\log(g_l f_{lu}) = -1.765$. There is another P II line at 1536.4157 Å, which is not considered while fitting the spectra because the line is blended with two relatively strong Ni II lines which likely have incorrect $\log(g_l f_{lu})$ values, based on a comparison with the Vega spectrum. We could not estimate the $\log(g_l f_{lu})$ values for the other P II line and the two Ni II lines. Using the χ^2 minimization technique described in Section 4.1, we estimated the P abundance from this spectral region to be $(P/H)_* = -7.56^{+0.32}_{-0.26}$ (3σ confidence; see Fig. B1, bottom panel). The best-fitting value here is within 1σ of the main result presented in Section 4.1.

Aside from noise in the spectrum, two other sources of uncertainty affect our P abundance measurements – uncertainty in our $\log(g_l f_{lu})$ values and the uncertainty in our continuum placement. For weak lines, the $\log(g_l f_{lu})$ of a spectral line is directly proportional to the inferred abundance of that element. Since our correction of $\log(g_l f_{lu})$ values for the P lines are based on the spectrum of Vega, we can use the P abundance uncertainty in Vega from Fitzpatrick (2010) to get the uncertainty in our $\log(g_l f_{lu})$. This gives an uncertainty of 0.05 dex in $\log(g_l f_{lu})$. The $\log(g_l f_{lu})$ value can also be affected by the S/N of the Vega spectrum. This uncertainty is ~ 0.06 dex. Assuming both uncertainties are uncorrelated, the combined uncertainty of the $\log(g_l f_{lu})$ value is ~ 0.08 dex. Thus, the uncertainty in our P abundance estimates of HD 100546 from $\log(g_l f_{lu})$ is 0.08 dex (1σ).

For the spectral regions discussed here and in Section 4.1, we shifted the continuum vertically to check its effect on the measured $(P/H)_*$. We found that a local continuum multiplier in excess of a factor of 1.005 makes the local spectral region inconsistent with the wider spectrum in terms of the low-order behaviour of the normalized spectrum. A continuum multiplier 1.005 in either direction for both spectral regions used to estimate $(P/H)_*$ changes the P abundance by $\approx \pm 0.11$ dex. This is smaller than the formal 3σ uncertainties we report for our results.

We did not consider here the uncertainty due to other stellar parameters and abundances since quantifying that is more complicated and was not considered as a source of uncertainty in Folsom et al. (2012). Although there might be additional sources of systematic uncertainties, such as incorrect $\log(g_l f_{lu})$ values of neighbouring blended lines, our comparison with the Vega spectrum suggests

that such factors cannot offset the P depletion implied by our measurement.

Figure B1. Determining $(P/H)_*$ for HD 100546 in a second spectral region. **Top panel:** the spectrum of HD 100546 at native (light grey) and binned resolution (dark grey), the three smooth curves are the best-fitting synthetic spectrum and its $\pm 3\sigma$ parameter deviations. The highlighted spectral region is used for estimating $\log(P/H)_*$ with chi-square minimization. **Bottom panel:** χ^2 as a function of $\log(P/H)_*$. The solid vertical line indicates the minimum and the adjacent dashed lines are $\pm 3\sigma$ confidence intervals. The solar and proto-solar values are shown for comparison.

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